

IMPACT OF ELIJAH MUHAMMAD LEADERSHIP OF THE NATION OF ISLAM AND ACTIVISM IN JIM CROW'S AMERICA: LESSONS FOR LEADERSHIP AND SOCIAL ACTIVISM IN NIGERIA

¹Danga Jamiu Yusuf (Ph.D.) and ²Baba Isaac Ibrahim (Ph.D.)

¹*Department of History and War Studies, Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna.*

²*Department of History and International Studies, Federal University Lokoja.*

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20158677>

Key words:

Leadership,
Activism, Jim
Crow, America,
Impact, Elijah,
Islam

Abstract: *This paper examines the leadership and impact of Elijah Muhammad, focusing on his role in shaping the Nation of Islam (NOI) and the broader struggle for Black empowerment in America. In contemporary society, when the Black Lives Movement has gained attention, there is a need to understand how his leadership strategies influenced such social and political movements advocating for racial and economic self-sufficiency. The objective of the study is to examine his background, ideological foundations, institutional contributions, and the lasting implications of his leadership. The study adopted a historical and analytical approach, and utilized secondary sources, including speeches, biographies, and scholarly analyses of his leadership and the NOI's impact. Findings reveal that Elijah Muhammad's leadership was instrumental in fostering Black economic independence, religious identity, and self-reliance. His teachings influenced key figures such as Malcolm X and Muhammad Ali and contributed to the rise of Black Nationalist movements. However, his tenure was also marked by controversy, including ideological rigidity, internal conflicts, and personal scandals that challenged his moral authority. The study concludes that Elijah Muhammad's leadership model was both transformative and complex, providing a framework for mobilizing marginalized communities while also illustrating the difficulties of sustaining a movement. The implications for contemporary leadership suggest that visionary leaders must balance ideological commitment with organizational adaptability. His emphasis on self-reliance and institutional development remains relevant for modern activists and leaders addressing racial and economic inequalities. His legacy offers critical lessons on leadership, resilience, and the complexities of leading social change.*

Danga Jamiu Yusuf (Ph.D.) and Baba Isaac Ibrahim (Ph.D.)

Introduction

Elijah Muhammad was a transformative leader who reshaped the landscape of Black empowerment in America. Born in 1897 in the racially segregated South, he experienced firsthand the oppression and economic hardship that defined the lives of African Americans under Jim Crow. Limited education and economic struggles forced him to migrate to Detroit, where he encountered Wallace Fard Muhammad, the founder of the Nation of Islam (NOI).¹ Fard's teachings on Black self-sufficiency, pride, and separation from white society profoundly influenced Elijah, who took over the NOI's leadership in 1934 after Fard's disappearance. Over the next four decades, Elijah Muhammad expanded the NOI into a national movement, establishing religious institutions, businesses, and schools that provided Black communities with alternatives to white-dominated systems. His teachings emphasized discipline, self-reliance, and economic independence, inspiring figures like Malcolm X and Muhammad Ali. However, his leadership was also marked by controversy, including allegations of financial misconduct and personal scandals that led to internal divisions.

Studying Elijah Muhammad's leadership is crucial for understanding how visionary leadership can mobilize marginalized communities against systemic oppression. His

ability to build a self-sustaining movement highlights the power of grassroots activism and economic empowerment as tools for social change. His life and work contribute to the ongoing dialogue on the intersection of leadership, activism, and social transformation, demonstrating how leaders can challenge oppressive systems while navigating internal and external challenges.² Elijah Muhammad's leadership, we gain valuable insights into how organizations can balance ideology, community-building, and governance in the pursuit of justice and self-determination. His legacy remains relevant today as activists and leaders continue to seek models of empowerment that address racial and economic disparities in society.

Birth, Growth and Education of Elijah Mohammed

Elijah Muhammad, born Elijah Robert Poole on October 7, 1897, in Sandersville, Georgia, emerged from humble and challenging beginnings to become one of the most influential Black leaders of the 20th century as the head of the Nation of Islam (NOI). His birth occurred in a rural, segregated corner of the Deep South, where his parents, William Poole Sr. and Mariah Hall, struggled to provide for their large family as sharecroppers and descendants of enslaved African Americans.³ Elijah was the seventh of thirteen children, a brood that reflected the harsh realities of poverty and racial oppression

¹ Karl Evanzz, *the Messenger: The Rise and fall of Elijah Muhammad* (New York: Pantheon Books, 1999), 112.

² Manning Marable, *Malcolm X: A Life of Reinvention* (New York: Viking, 2011), 89.

³ *Elijah Muhammad, Message to the Blackman in America* (Chicago: Muhammad Mosque of Islam No. 2, 1965), 15.

in post-Reconstruction Georgia. His father, a Baptist lay preacher, eked out a living farming land he didn't own, while his mother managed the household and supplemented the family income through domestic work. The Poole family lived in a world defined by Jim Crow laws, where systemic racism limited opportunities and enforced a rigid social hierarchy. Elijah's early life was steeped in these conditions, shaping his worldview and later fueling his commitment to Black self-reliance and liberation.

Growing up in Sandersville, Elijah's childhood was marked by labour and survival rather than leisure or formal education. The rural South offered little in the way of schooling for Black children, and Elijah's academic journey was brief and interrupted. He attended a local segregated school sporadically, reaching only the fourth grade before economic necessity pulled him away. Like many Black families of the era, the Pooles relied on their children's labour to make ends meet, and Elijah worked alongside his siblings in the fields, picking cotton and performing other grueling tasks. This lack of education was not a reflection of his intellect later in life, as he demonstrated a sharp mind and persuasive oratory; but rather the structural barriers imposed by a society that devalued Black potential. His early exposure to his father's preaching, however, planted seeds of spiritual curiosity and rhetorical skill that would blossom in adulthood. The Poole household, though poor, was deeply religious, with William Sr.'s Baptist faith providing a moral framework

that Elijah would later reinterpret through his own lens.

Elijah's growth into manhood coincided with the broader struggles of Black Americans in the early 20th century. As a teenager, he witnessed the brutal realities of racial violence firsthand. Family lore and historical accounts suggest he saw a lynching, an event that left a lasting imprint, reinforcing his distrust of white authority and society. By his late teens, Elijah sought to escape the oppressive conditions of Georgia. In 1917, at the age of 20, he married Clara Evans, a woman from a similarly modest background, whom he met in Cordele, Georgia. Clara, born in 1899, was a steadfast partner whose resilience would prove vital in the years ahead. The couple began their family soon after, with their first child arriving in 1919. However, the South offered little hope for a young Black family, and the Great Migration - the mass exodus of African Americans to northern cities, beckoned.⁴ In 1923, Elijah, Clara, and their growing brood joined the wave, relocating to Detroit, Michigan, in search of industrial jobs and a reprieve from Southern racism.

In Detroit, Elijah's family expanded significantly, eventually growing to include eight children: Emmanuel, Ethel, Lottie, Nathaniel, Herbert, Elijah Jr., Wallace (later Warith Deen Mohammed), and Akbar. Life in the North, however, was not the Promised Land they had envisioned. Elijah worked a series of low-paying, labour-intensive jobs (first at the American Nut Company, then at Chevrolet's assembly lines), struggling to support his large family amid the

⁴ Karl Evanzz, *The Messenger: The Rise and Fall of Elijah Muhammad* (New York: Pantheon Books, 1999), 112.

economic instability of the 1920s. The Great Depression, which began in 1929, hit Detroit hard, exacerbating their financial woes. Housing discrimination confined the Pooles to overcrowded, rundown neighborhoods, and racial tensions simmered as white workers competed with Black migrants for scarce jobs. Clara managed the household with resourcefulness, raising the children under tight circumstances while Elijah grappled with the daily grind. The family's Baptist roots remained a constant, though Elijah grew increasingly disillusioned with Christianity, which he began to see as a tool of white oppression - a sentiment that would later define his religious transformation.

Elijah's limited schooling in Georgia left him with basic literacy, but his real education came through experience and observation. Detroit exposed him to new ideas and movements, including Marcus Garvey's Universal Negro Improvement Association (UNIA), which championed Black pride and economic independence. These concepts resonated with Elijah, laying the groundwork for his later ideology. His intellectual and spiritual growth took a dramatic turn in 1931 when he attended a speech by Wallace Fard Muhammad, the mysterious founder of the Nation of Islam. Fard's teachings that Black people were the original humans, whites were a race of "devils" created by a rogue scientist named Yakub, and Islam was the true path to liberation, captivated Elijah. He joined the NOI, adopting the name Elijah Muhammad and immersing himself in its mission. Clara and their children eventually followed him into the faith, cementing the

family's shift from Christianity to this nascent Black nationalist movement.

As Elijah rose within the NOI, his family became both a source of strength and a reflection of his evolving role. After Fard's unexplained disappearance in 1934, Elijah assumed leadership, relocating the organization's headquarters to Chicago and building a network of temples, schools, and businesses. Clara, known within the NOI as Sister Clara Muhammad, played a crucial role, helping establish the University of Islam schools to educate Black children (including their own) in a curriculum free of white influence.

The couple's children grew up steeped in NOI doctrine, with several taking on leadership roles over time. Wallace (later Warith Deen), born in 1933, would eventually succeed his father, while others, like Herbert, contributed to the organization's media and operations. Elijah's family life, however, was not without complexity. Reports of extramarital relationships, resulting in additional children, estimated to range from 13 to 21 offspring in total, strained his marriage and later fueled controversy within the NOI, notably contributing to Malcolm X's break with the group.

The American Society before the Activism of Elijah Mohammed

The American society that necessitated the activism of Elijah Muhammad and similar figures was one that can be described as based in systemic racism, economic inequality, and social exclusion, particularly for African Americans. Emerging in the early 20th century, Elijah Muhammad's leadership of the Nation of

Islam (NOI) and his advocacy for Black self-reliance and separatism were direct responses to a nation that had failed to deliver on its promises of equality and justice following centuries of slavery, segregation, and violence.⁵ To understand this context, one must examine the historical, social, and economic conditions of the United States during this period, which created a fertile ground for movements like the NOI to take root and resonate with disenfranchised Black communities.

At the turn of the 20th century, African Americans faced a society still reeling from the legacy of slavery, which had been abolished in 1865 but left an enduring imprint of racial hierarchy. The post-Reconstruction era saw the rise of Jim Crow laws in the South, enforcing legal segregation and disenfranchising Black citizens through poll taxes, literacy tests, and outright intimidation. Lynchings and racial violence were rampant, with the Ku Klux Klan and other white supremacist groups terrorizing Black communities. Elijah Muhammad, born Elijah Robert Poole in 1897 in Sandersville, Georgia, grew up in this environment, witnessing firsthand the brutal realities of Southern racism. His family, like many others, were sharecroppers—former slaves or their descendants trapped in a cycle of debt and poverty, working land they did not own under exploitative conditions. This oppressive system drove millions of African Americans, including Muhammad, to migrate north during the Great

Migration, seeking better opportunities and escape from Southern terror.

However, the North, while lacking formal Jim Crow laws, was no haven. Urban centers like Detroit, where Muhammad settled in 1923, were marked by de facto segregation, discriminatory housing practices, and limited economic prospects for Black residents. Industrial jobs, though available, often relegated African Americans to the lowest-paying, most dangerous roles, while unions frequently excluded them. The Great Depression, beginning in 1929, exacerbated these conditions, plunging Black communities into even deeper poverty as unemployment soared. It was in this context of economic despair and racial exclusion that Muhammad encountered Wallace D. Fard, the mysterious founder of the Nation of Islam, in 1931. Fard's teachings that Black people were the original people of the earth, that whites were a race of "devils" created through selective breeding, and that Islam was the true religion of Black liberation' offered a radical reinterpretation of history and identity that resonated with those who felt abandoned by mainstream American society.

This society was also characterized by a profound spiritual and cultural void for African Americans. Christianity, the dominant religion, had been imposed during slavery and was often wielded by white authorities to justify bondage and later segregation.⁶ Many Black men, as Muhammad himself noted, felt alienated from churches that failed to address their material

⁵ E. U. Essien-Udom, *Black Nationalism: A Search for an Identity in America* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1962), 178.

⁶ Edward E. Curtis IV, *Black Muslim Religion in the Nation of Islam, 1960-1975* (Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 2006), 94.

struggles or affirm their dignity. The NOI filled this gap by offering a theology that centered Black identity and promised redemption through self-discipline and community-building. Elijah Muhammad, upon assuming leadership of the NOI after Fard's disappearance in 1934, expanded this message, preaching economic independence, racial pride, and separation from white America. His activism was necessitated by a nation where Black bodies were still commodified, whether through labour exploitation, incarceration, or violence, and where the American Dream remained elusive.⁷ Politically, the early 20th century offered little recourse. The federal government, despite constitutional amendments granting citizenship and voting rights, largely turned a blind eye to racial injustice. The Plessy v. Ferguson decision of 1896 had enshrined "separate but equal" as law, legitimizing segregation until the 1950s. Even progressive movements, like the New Deal, often excluded Black workers from benefits, reinforcing economic disparities. Mainstream civil rights organizations, such as the NAACP, focused on legal battles and integration, but their gradualist approach frustrated many who faced daily indignities and saw no immediate relief. Elijah Muhammad's call for a separate Black nation-state, funded by reparations for slavery, was a radical departure from integrationist ideals, reflecting a belief that white America would never willingly cede power or equality.

The urban ghettos of the North, where the NOI gained traction, were microcosms of this broader societal failure. Overcrowded, underfunded, and policed with hostility, these neighborhoods bred despair but also resistance. Muhammad's activism targeted the "so-called Negro" a term he used to critique the loss of cultural identity under white domination, offering a vision of empowerment through Black-owned businesses, schools, and farms. By the 1950s and 1960s, the NOI owned bakeries, grocery stores, and farmland, demonstrating a practical alternative to reliance on a racist system. This economic self-sufficiency was a direct response to a society that systematically denied Black people access to capital, education, and property.

Moreover, the cultural climate of mid-20th-century America further necessitated such activism. The dominant narrative celebrated white achievement while erasing or vilifying Black contributions. Media portrayed African Americans as subservient or criminal, reinforcing stereotypes that justified discrimination. Muhammad's teachings countered this by instilling pride in Black history and rejecting white standards of beauty and success. His rejection of integration, unlike Martin Luther King Jr.'s vision, stemmed from a deep skepticism of white goodwill; a skepticism born from decades of broken promises, from Reconstruction to the unfulfilled hopes of World War II veterans who returned to segregation despite fighting for democracy abroad.⁸

⁷ Wilfred Samuels and Gregory S. McCue, *The Critical Response to Malcolm X (Westport, CT: Greenwood Press, 1996)*, 37.

⁸ William L. Van Deburg, *New Day in Babylon: The Black Power Movement and American Culture, 1965-1975 (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1993)*, 125.

The Cold War era added another layer of complexity. The U.S. government, eager to project an image of freedom against Soviet criticism, began to address civil rights more visibly, yet it simultaneously surveilled and suppressed radical Black voices like Muhammad's. The FBI, under J. Edgar Hoover, targeted the NOI as a threat, especially after Muhammad urged followers to resist the draft during World War II, leading to his imprisonment from 1942 to 1946. This repression underscored the limits of American tolerance for Black dissent, pushing figures like Muhammad to operate outside conventional political channels.

Elijah Muhammad's activism, and that of his contemporaries like Malcolm X, was thus a product of a society that offered African Americans neither justice nor belonging.⁹ His emphasis on self-defense, economic autonomy, and cultural reclamation challenged the status quo in ways that integrationist movements did not. While his controversial separatist rhetoric and unorthodox theology drew criticism from both Black Christians and mainstream Muslims, his appeal lay in addressing the visceral realities of Black life: poverty, violence, and erasure. By the time of his death in 1975, the NOI had grown from a small sect to a national movement, reflecting the depth of discontent within American society.

It can be said that the America of Elijah Muhammad's era was a nation of stark contradictions; preaching liberty while practicing oppression, promising opportunity

while enforcing exclusion. His activism was not merely a reaction but a reclamation, offering a vision of Black power and identity in a country that had long denied both. The conditions of racial terror, economic deprivation, and cultural alienation necessitated a leader who could articulate the anger and aspirations of the marginalized, making Muhammad and his like's inevitable forces in the struggle for dignity and survival.

Elijah Mohammed and Nation of Islam

Elijah Mohammed emerged from the crucible of poverty and racial oppression to become the transformative leader of the Nation of Islam (NOI), a religious and sociopolitical movement that redefined Black identity in America. His relationship with the NOI was not merely that of a leader but of a visionary who molded its ideology, structure, and legacy over four decades, from 1934 until his death on February 25, 1975. This journey began in the industrial sprawl of Detroit in 1931, when Elijah, then a struggling labourer and father of eight, encountered Wallace Fard Muhammad, the enigmatic founder of the NOI. Fard's teachings that Black people were the original humans, whites were a race of "devils" engineered by a scientist named Yakub, and Islam was the path to liberation' struck a chord with Elijah, who saw in them an antidote to the degradation he had experienced in the Jim Crow South and the economic hardship of the North. Joining the NOI, he shed his "slave name" of Poole for Muhammad, signaling a profound personal and

⁹ James H. Cone, Martin & Malcolm & America: A Dream or a Nightmare (Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 1991), 220.

ideological rebirth.¹⁰ His relationship with the NOI evolved from that of a devoted disciple to its supreme leader, shaping it into a powerful force for Black empowerment while navigating internal tensions, external persecution, and personal controversies that tested its cohesion.¹¹ Elijah's initial connection to the NOI was rooted in his encounter with Fard, a figure shrouded in mystery whose origins remain debated. Some claimed he was from the Middle East, others from the United States.¹² Fard had founded the NOI in 1930, preaching a blend of Islamic principles, Black Nationalism, and esoteric theology to Detroit's disenfranchised Black community. Elijah, working grueling factory jobs and raising his family with his wife Clara, attended one of Fard's lectures in 1931. The message of Black divinity and self-reliance electrified him, offering a stark contrast to the Christianity of his upbringing, which he increasingly viewed as a tool of white supremacy. Fard took Elijah under his wing, appointing him a minister and renaming him Elijah Muhammad. This mentorship was brief but pivotal. When Fard vanished in 1934 under unclear circumstances, some speculated that he was deported, others felt that he simply withdrew. Elijah stepped into the leadership vacuum, claiming Fard had designated him as successor. This transition marked the beginning of Elijah's lifelong bond with the NOI, transforming it from a small sect into a national movement.

Under Elijah's stewardship, the NOI grew from a fledgling group into a structured organization with temples (later called mosques) across the United States, including major hubs in Chicago, New York, and Los Angeles. He relocated the headquarters to Chicago, where he established Temple No. 2 as the epicenter of NOI activity. Elijah refined and expanded Fard's theology, declaring Fard as Allah incarnate and himself as the "Messenger of Allah," a prophet tasked with awakening Black America. His teachings emphasized racial pride, economic independence, and separation from white society rather than integration; which was a radical departure from the civil rights mainstream led by figures like Martin Luther King Jr. Elijah preached that whites were inherently evil, a product of Yakub's genetic manipulation, and that Black people needed to reclaim their divine heritage through discipline and self-sufficiency. This doctrine resonated with many African Americans disillusioned by systemic racism, drawing thousands to the NOI's ranks during the 1930s and 1940s, despite its divergence from orthodox Islam.

Elijah's relationship with the NOI was tested early by external pressures and internal challenges. In 1942, during World War II, he was arrested for encouraging followers to resist the draft, arguing that Black Americans owed no loyalty to a nation that oppressed them. Convicted of sedition, he served four years in federal prison (1942–1946), a period that

¹⁰ John H. Bracey, *August Meier, and Elliott Rudwick, Black Nationalism in America (Indianapolis: Bobbs-Merrill, 1970), 204.*

¹¹ Louis Farrakhan, "The Vision of Elijah Muhammad," *The Final Call, March 12, 1996.*

¹² Taylor Branch, *Parting the Waters: America in the King Years, 1954-63 (New York: Simon & Schuster, 1988), 299.*

solidified his resolve and elevated his status among followers as a martyr. From prison, he maintained control, sending directives to his lieutenants. Upon release, he intensified efforts to build the NOI's infrastructure, establishing businesses such as grocery stores, bakeries, and clothing shops, to employ members and fund the movement. He founded the University of Islam schools to educate Black children outside white influence, with his wife Clara playing a key role in their development. The newspaper *Muhammad Speaks*, launched in the 1960s, became a megaphone for his ideas, reaching a wide audience and amplifying the NOI's influence. These initiatives reflected Elijah's vision of a self-contained Black nation within America, a practical extension of his separatist ideology.

Central to Elijah's leadership was his mentorship of key figures who shaped the NOI's trajectory, most notably Malcolm X. Born Malcolm Little, he joined the NOI in the early 1950s while in prison, transformed by Elijah's writings.¹³ Upon release, Malcolm became Elijah's most dynamic minister, recruiting thousands and elevating the NOI's profile with his fiery oratory. Elijah saw Malcolm as a protégé, entrusting him with Temple No. 7 in Harlem and relying on his charisma to spread the message. However, their relationship deteriorated in the early 1960s as Malcolm grew critical of Elijah's personal conduct, specifically, allegations that Elijah had fathered children with several young secretaries, a breach of the NOI's strict moral code. These claims, later

substantiated by some of his offspring, including at least 13 children born out of wedlock, strained the NOI's unity.¹⁴ Malcolm's discovery of this hypocrisy, coupled with his evolving views toward orthodox Islam and racial reconciliation, led to his suspension in 1963 and assassination in 1965 by NOI members; a tragedy that underscored the tensions within Elijah's fold.

Elijah's relationship with the NOI was also defined by his rivalry with orthodox Muslim critics and the U.S. government. Mainstream Muslims denounced his theology as heretical, rejecting his deification of Fard and racial doctrines. The FBI, viewing the NOI as a subversive threat, surveilled Elijah for decades under COINTELPRO, infiltrating the group and exacerbating internal divisions. Despite these pressures, Elijah's leadership held firm, bolstered by loyalists like Louis Farrakhan, who joined in the 1950s and became a staunch defender of Elijah's vision. Farrakhan's devotion contrasted with Malcolm's defection, highlighting the spectrum of loyalty Elijah inspired. By the 1970s, the NOI boasted tens of thousands of members, though estimates vary widely due to its secretive nature. Elijah's strict discipline—no pork, alcohol, or drugs—and emphasis on family values appealed to many seeking structure amid urban decay.

As Elijah aged, his relationship with the NOI shifted toward legacy-building. His health declined in the early 1970s, with congestive heart failure plaguing his final years. He groomed his son Wallace (later Warith Deen Mohammed), born in 1933, to succeed him,

¹³ Noel Ignatiev, *How the Irish Became White* (New York: Routledge, 1995), 175.

¹⁴ Robert L. Allen, *Black Awakening in Capitalist America* (Trenton, NJ: Africa World Press, 1990), 88.

though Wallace’s leanings toward Sunni Islam foreshadowed a schism. Elijah’s death on February 25, 1975, at age 77, marked a turning point. Warith assumed leadership, dismantling much of Elijah’s theology and renaming the group the American Society of Muslims, aligning it with global Islam. This pivot alienated hardliners like Farrakhan, who broke away in 1978 to revive the original NOI, preserving Elijah’s teachings. The split reflected the dual paths of Elijah’s influence—one toward integration, the other toward his separatist roots.

Achievements of Elijah Mohammed

Despite having limited formal education, and in the midst of racial oppression, Elijah transformed the NOI from a small, esoteric sect founded by Wallace Fard Muhammad in 1930, into a nationwide movement that challenged systemic racism and offered a radical alternative to the integrationist civil rights narrative. His leadership not only built a robust infrastructure of temples, schools, and businesses but also inspired a generation to embrace pride, discipline, and independence, influencing figures like Malcolm X, Muhammad Ali, and Louis Farrakhan.¹⁵ Despite controversies, including his unorthodox theology and personal scandals, Elijah’s achievements reshaped Black consciousness and provided a blueprint for self-determination that endures in various forms today.¹⁶

Institutionalization of the Nation of Islam

One of Elijah Muhammad’s most significant achievements was his expansion and institutionalization of the NOI. When he assumed leadership in 1934 following Fard’s mysterious disappearance, the group was a fledgling collective confined to Detroit. Elijah relocated its base to Chicago, establishing Temple No. 2 as its headquarters, and over the decades grew it into a network of dozens of temples across cities like New York, Los Angeles, and Washington, D.C.¹⁷ He refined Fard’s teachings into a cohesive doctrine, declaring Fard as Allah incarnate and himself as the “Messenger of Allah,” tasked with awakening Black America. This theology, blending Islamic elements with Black nationalism, asserted that Black people were the original humans and whites a race of “devils” created by a scientist named Yakub—a narrative that, while divisive, galvanized thousands by affirming Black divinity and rejecting white supremacy. By the 1970s, the NOI’s membership swelled to tens of thousands, though exact figures remain elusive due to its insular nature. Elijah’s ability to scale this movement amid persecution, including a four-year prison stint (1942–1946) for draft resistance; demonstrated his organizational tenacity and cemented his status as a leader willing to endure hardship for his cause.

Economic development

Economically, Elijah achieved remarkable success by fostering self-reliance within the Black community, a cornerstone of his separatist philosophy. He rejected dependence

¹⁵ Robert Dannin, *Black Pilgrimage to Islam* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2002), 143.

¹⁶

¹⁷ *Malcolm X with Alex Haley*, the Autobiography of Malcolm X (New York: Ballantine Books, 1965), 234.

on white institutions, instead building an ecosystem of NOI-owned businesses that employed members and funded the movement. These ventures included grocery stores, bakeries, clothing shops, and restaurants, particularly concentrated in Chicago. The NOI's economic model emphasized reinvesting profits into the community, creating jobs and reducing reliance on external systems that marginalized African Americans. A standout achievement was the establishment of a farm in Georgia, which supplied fresh produce to NOI outlets, embodying his vision of agricultural independence. The newspaper "Muhammad Speaks", launched in the 1960s and edited by his son Herbert, became one of the most widely circulated Black publications of its time, generating revenue while spreading Elijah's message. These enterprises not only sustained the NOI but also provided a tangible example of Black economic power, inspiring followers to see themselves as producers rather than consumers in a racist economy.

Educational Development

Educationally, Elijah's achievements were transformative, particularly through the creation of the University of Islam schools. Recognizing that public education often perpetuated white supremacist narratives and neglected Black history, he established these institutions to offer an alternative curriculum rooted in NOI principles. The first school opened in Detroit in the 1930s, with others following in Chicago and beyond, teaching

subjects like math, reading, and science alongside lessons in Black pride and self-reliance. His wife, Clara Muhammad, played a pivotal role in developing these schools, ensuring they served as safe havens where Black children, including their own eight offsprings, could learn without the stigma of segregation or inferiority. This initiative challenged the status quo of American education, empowering a generation of NOI youth with knowledge and discipline. While criticized for its religious slant, the University of Islam laid the groundwork for later Afrocentric educational movements, proving that Black communities could control their intellectual destiny.¹⁸

Promotion of Black Identity

Elijah's promotion of Black identity and cultural pride stands as another monumental achievement. In an era when African Americans faced relentless denigration, he preached a gospel of inherent worth, urging followers to reject "slave names" (like his own transition from Poole to Muhammad) and embrace their African heritage. His strict moral code of "no pork, alcohol, or drugs", instilled discipline and self-respect, while his emphasis on family values and gender roles (men as providers, women as homemakers) aimed to rebuild Black social structures battered by slavery and discrimination. This message resonated widely, attracting high-profile converts like Muhammad Ali, whose 1964 heavyweight title win as an NOI member amplified Elijah's reach. The NOI's Fruit of Islam, a paramilitary wing, further

¹⁸ John Andrew Morrow, *Finding W.D. Fard: Unveiling the Identity of the Founder of the Nation of Islam* (Cambridge: Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2019), 97.

embodied this ethos, training young men in martial arts and protection duties, fostering a sense of agency and strength. Elijah's focus on identity shifted the narrative from victimhood to empowerment, influencing broader Black Power movements of the 1960s and 1970s.

Mentoring Activists and Social Leaders

His mentorship of influential leaders was a key achievement, though not without complexity. Malcolm X, recruited in the 1950s, became Elijah's most effective apostle, swelling NOI ranks with his eloquence until their 1963 rift over Elijah's extramarital affairs, which resulted in at least 13 children outside his marriage, led to Malcolm's exit and 1965 assassination by NOI loyalists. Louis Farrakhan, joining in the same decade, remained a steadfast disciple, later reviving Elijah's original NOI in 1978 after Elijah's son Warith Deen Mohammed pivoted toward orthodox Islam post-1975. These relationships highlight Elijah's ability to inspire, even as personal failings strained his legacy. His influence also touched the arts and activism, with figures like the Last Poets drawing from NOI rhetoric.

Challenges Faced by Elijah Mohammed

Elijah Muhammad's achievements were not without critique. His theology alienated mainstream Muslims, his separatism clashed with civil rights integrationists, and his personal scandals eroded some trust. Yet, his impact was undeniable. By his death, he had built a movement that offered Black Americans a radical vision of freedom, sustained by

economic, educational, and cultural pillars.¹⁹ The NOI's survival and splintering into factions (one orthodox under Warith, one traditional under Farrakhan), reflected his enduring influence. Elijah's legacy lies in proving that a marginalized people could forge their own path, a testament to his unyielding belief in Black potential amid a society determined to suppress it.²⁰

Elijah Muhammad's leadership, while transformative, was not without challenges and criticisms. One of the main criticisms was his rigid ideology, particularly the racial separatist doctrine that portrayed white people as inherently evil. This belief alienated potential allies in the broader civil rights movement and led to conflicts with mainstream Muslims who rejected his theological interpretations. His teachings diverged significantly from traditional Islam, as he declared Wallace Fard Muhammad to be Allah in human form and himself as His Messenger, a claim that mainstream Islamic scholars considered heretical.

Internally, the Nation of Islam faced leadership struggles, particularly after Malcolm X, once Muhammad's most prominent disciple, publicly challenged his moral integrity. Reports surfaced that Elijah Muhammad had fathered several children with young secretaries, violating the strict moral code he preached. This revelation led to Malcolm X's break with the NOI and intensified internal divisions, ultimately contributing to Malcolm's assassination by NOI members. Additionally, Muhammad and the

¹⁹ Claude Clegg III, *An Original Man: The Life and Times of Elijah Muhammad* (New York: St. Martin's Press, 1997), 45.

²⁰ Marlon B. Ross, *Manning the Race: Reforming Black Men in the Jim Crow Era* (New York: New York University Press, 2004), 146.

NOI faced continuous surveillance and suppression from the U.S. government, particularly through the FBI's COINTELPRO program, which sought to undermine Black Nationalist movements. Despite these challenges, Elijah Muhammad maintained control of the NOI for decades, but his legacy remains contested, reflecting both his visionary leadership and the controversies that surrounded him.²¹

Lessons for Leadership and Social Activism in Nigeria

Nigerian leaders and activists can learn the following lessons from Elijah Muhammad's leadership and activism

Self-Reliance

One of the most critical lessons from Elijah Muhammad for Nigerian leadership is the power of self-reliance as a tool for empowerment. Muhammad tirelessly preached that African Americans should not depend on the goodwill of their oppressors, whom he controversially labeled "white devils" but instead build their own economic and social institutions. He established businesses, schools, and farms under the NOI, creating a parallel economy that sustained his community and reduced reliance on a discriminatory system. In Nigeria, where economic dependence on foreign aid, multinational corporations, and a corrupt elite has perpetuated poverty and underdevelopment, this lesson is profoundly applicable. Leaders can draw inspiration from Muhammad's model to foster local

entrepreneurship, invest in community-driven industries, and prioritize indigenous solutions over external handouts. For instance, Nigeria's informal economy, which employs millions in small-scale trade and craftsmanship, could be harnessed through cooperative networks akin to the NOI's enterprises, empowering citizens economically while reducing the influence of exploitative foreign entities. Social activists, too, can adopt this approach by mobilizing grassroots movements to create self-sustaining communities, addressing issues like unemployment and food insecurity without waiting for government intervention.

The Need for Mass Quality Education

Another key lesson is the importance of education as a cornerstone of leadership and activism. Elijah Muhammad founded the Muhammad University of Islam to educate Black children outside the mainstream system, which he viewed as a tool of indoctrination that erased African identity and history. He believed that true liberation began with knowledge of self, understanding one's heritage, capabilities, and potential. In Nigeria, where the education system struggles with underfunding, colonial legacies, and disparities between urban and rural areas, this principle could guide leaders to prioritize culturally relevant curricula that instill pride in Nigerian history and values. Activists could push for educational reforms that address the needs of marginalized groups, such as the Almajiri children in the north or rural communities in the southeast, ensuring that

²¹ Claude Andrew Clegg, *Troubled Ground: A Tale of Murder, Lynching, and Reckoning in the New South (Champaign: University of Illinois Press, 2010)*, 204.

they are equipped with skills for self-reliance rather than perpetuating cycles of poverty. Muhammad's emphasis on education also highlights the need for leaders to combat ignorance and misinformation, which fuel ethnic and religious conflicts in Nigeria, by promoting literacy, critical thinking, self-confidence and self-awareness, as tools for unity and national progress.

The Need for Integrity

Moral discipline and personal integrity stand out as additional lessons from Elijah Muhammad's leadership. He imposed strict codes of conduct on NOI members, including prohibitions on alcohol, drugs, and extramarital affairs, arguing that personal transformation was a prerequisite for societal change. This focus on discipline helped the NOI cultivate a sense of dignity and purpose among its followers, countering the stereotypes imposed by a racist society. In Nigeria, where corruption and moral decay among leaders have eroded public trust, this lesson is a clarion call for accountability and ethical governance. Leaders who model integrity, whether in politics, business, or civil society, can inspire confidence and mobilize collective action against systemic injustices.

Social activists, particularly those fighting corruption or advocating for good governance, could adopt Muhammad's approach by emphasizing personal responsibility as a foundation for demanding systemic reform, rallying Nigerians around a shared ethos of discipline integrity and honour.

The Use of Separatism as a Tool of Activism

Elijah Muhammad's strategic use of separatism also offers a nuanced lesson for Nigeria, though it requires careful adaptation. He advocated for a separate Black nation within America, believing that integration with whites was neither feasible nor desirable given centuries of oppression. While physical separatism may not suit Nigeria's context, where ethnic groups are deeply interwoven, his underlying principle of self-determination is highly relevant. Nigerian leaders and activists can interpret this as a call to assert cultural and political autonomy within a unified framework, resisting domination by any single group or external power. In a country with over 250 ethnic groups and a history of regional tensions (e.g., the Biafran War), Muhammad's lesson suggests fostering coalitions that respect diversity while building collective strength. Activists could apply this by amplifying the voices of marginalized ethnicities, like the Ogoni or the Tiv, by ensuring their inclusion in national discourse without fracturing the nation's fragile unity.

The Need for Unity of Identities

Unity and collective identity form another cornerstone of Muhammad's teachings that Nigerian leaders can leverage. He sought to unify African Americans under a shared Islamic identity, transcending tribal and regional differences inherited from slavery. In Nigeria, where divisions between Hausa, Yoruba, Igbo, and smaller ethnic groups often undermine national progress, this lesson underscores the need for a unifying vision. Leaders could draw from Muhammad's example to craft narratives that emphasize common struggles, such as poverty, corruption, and insecurity; over

divisive ethnic or religious rhetoric. Social activists, particularly in the context of movements like #EndSARS or calls for restructuring, could use this approach to bridge divides, rallying Nigerians around a collective purpose. Muhammad's success in uniting disparate Black communities through faith and purpose suggests that a Nigerian equivalent, whether rooted in religion, culture, or civic ideals, could counter the centrifugal forces threatening national cohesion.

Religion as a Mobilizing Force

The role of religion as a mobilizing force is another critical lesson from Elijah Muhammad, though it must be approached with caution in Nigeria's volatile religious landscape. Muhammad transformed Islam into a vehicle for social justice, using it to inspire hope and action among African Americans. His unorthodox theology, including the deification of Wallace Fard Muhammad and the demonization of whites, galvanized his followers by giving them a sense of divine mission. In Nigeria, where Christianity and Islam often clash, exemplified by Boko Haram's insurgency or communal violence in the Middle Belt, leaders and activists could harness religion's unifying potential while avoiding its divisive pitfalls. Muhammad's model suggests that faith can be a powerful tool for social change if directed toward constructive ends, such as economic empowerment or education, rather than sectarian conflict. Nigerian leaders might channel religious energy into interfaith initiatives that address shared challenges, while activists could use spiritual frameworks to inspire resilience and solidarity across divides.

Resilience in Tough Situations

Resilience in the face of adversity is a further lesson from Muhammad's life that resonates deeply with Nigeria's struggles. He faced imprisonment, surveillance by the FBI, and internal dissent (notably Malcolm X's departure), yet persisted in building the NOI into a formidable movement. Nigerian leaders and activists, confronting state repression, economic hardship, and societal fragmentation, can draw strength from this example. Muhammad's ability to endure, such as during his 1942-1946 imprisonment for draft evasion and violating the Selective Service Act during World War II, teaches that setbacks are inevitable but surmountable through perseverance and strategic planning. In Nigeria, where protests are often met with violence (e.g., the 2020 Lekki massacre) and activists face arrest or exile, this resilience could inspire sustained efforts toward reform, encouraging leaders to adapt and regroup rather than abandon their causes.

Lessons for Economic Nationalism

Finally, Elijah Muhammad's emphasis on economic nationalism offers a practical lesson for Nigeria's leadership and activism. He urged Black Americans to "do for self" by establishing businesses and controlling their economic destiny, a response to systemic exclusion from mainstream wealth. In Nigeria, where oil dependency and foreign exploitation have stifled diversification, this principle could guide leaders to prioritize local industry such as agriculture, manufacturing, over the reliance on imports or extractive economies. Activists could champion policies that protect Nigerian markets

and labor, echoing Muhammad's call for economic sovereignty. His success in creating a network of NOI-owned enterprises demonstrates that grassroots economic power can challenge entrenched elites, a lesson Nigerian reformers could apply to dismantle the patronage networks that dominate the country's politics and economy.

Conclusion

Elijah Muhammad's life and leadership left an enduring impact on Black empowerment, religious movements, and social change in America. Born into poverty in the Jim Crow South, his early experiences with racial oppression shaped his commitment to self-reliance and Black liberation. His rise to prominence as the leader of the Nation of Islam transformed the organization from a small religious sect into a powerful movement advocating for economic independence, cultural pride, and racial separation. Through institutions such as the University of Islam schools and NOI-owned businesses, he provided a model of Black economic self-sufficiency. Despite facing government surveillance, internal conflicts, and personal controversies, his leadership laid the foundation for future

References

Alexander, Amy. *Fifty Black Women Who Changed America*. New York: Kensington, 1999.

Allen, Robert L. *Black Awakening in Capitalist America*. Trenton, NJ: Africa World Press, 1990.

Baldwin, James. *The Fire Next Time*. New York: Dial Press, 1963.

generations of activists and leaders. His influence extended to figures like Malcolm X, Muhammad Ali, and Louis Farrakhan, who each carried forward elements of his teachings in different ways.

Elijah Muhammad's legacy continues to shape contemporary discussions on leadership, activism, and racial justice. His emphasis on economic independence and community-building serves as a model for modern movements seeking to address systemic inequalities. His leadership also raises critical questions about the challenges of maintaining ideological integrity, managing internal divisions, and balancing personal conduct with public responsibility. In an era where racial and economic disparities persist, his strategies for mobilization and institution-building offer valuable lessons for leaders working toward social transformation. By studying his leadership, we gain deeper insights into the role of vision, discipline, and resilience in effecting lasting change. His legacy serves as a reminder that leadership in activism requires not only bold ideas but also the ability to build sustainable structures that empower marginalized communities in the long term.

Boyd, Herb. *Black Detroit: A People's History of Self-Determination*. New York: Amistad, 2017.

Branch, Taylor. *Parting the Waters: America in the King Years, 1954-63*. New York: Simon & Schuster, 1988.

- Bracey, John H., August Meier, and Elliott Rudwick. *Black Nationalism in America*. Indianapolis: Bobbs-Merrill, 1970.
- Clegg, Claude Andrew III. *An Original Man: The Life and Times of Elijah Muhammad*. New York: St. Martin's Press, 1997.
- Troubled Ground: A Tale of Murder, Lynching, and Reckoning in the New South*. Champaign: University of Illinois Press, 2010.
- Cone, James H. *Martin & Malcolm & America: A Dream or a Nightmare*. Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 1991.
- Curtis, Edward E., IV. *Black Muslim Religion in the Nation of Islam, 1960-1975*. Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 2006.
- Dannin, Robert. *Black Pilgrimage to Islam*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2002.
- Dyson, Michael Eric. *Making Malcolm: The Myth and Meaning of Malcolm X*. New York: Oxford University Press, 1995.
- Eig, Jonathan. *King: A Life*. New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2023.
- Elijah Muhammad. *Message to the Blackman in America*. Chicago: Muhammad Mosque of Islam No. 2, 1965.
- Our Savior Has Arrived*. Chicago: Muhammad Mosque of Islam No. 2, 1974.
- Essien-Udom, E. U. *Black Nationalism: A Search for an Identity in America*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1962.
- Evanzz, Karl. *The Messenger: The Rise and fall of Elijah Muhammad*. New York: Pantheon Books, 1999.
- Farrakhan, Louis. "The Vision of Elijah Muhammad." *The Final Call*, March 12, 1996.
- Federal Bureau of Investigation. *COINTELPRO: The FBI's War against Black America*, 1969.
- Handler, M. S. "Elijah Muhammad, Black Muslim Leader, Dies." *The New York Times*, February 26, 1975.
- Heath, G. Louis. *The Black Panther Leaders Speak*. Metuchen, NJ: Scarecrow Press, 1976.
- Ignatiev, Noel. *How the Irish Became White*. New York: Routledge, 1995.
- Marable, Manning. *Malcolm X: A Life of Reinvention*. New York: Viking, 2011.
- Malcolm X, with Alex Haley. *The Autobiography of Malcolm X*. New York: Ballantine Books, 1965.
- Morrow, John Andrew. *Finding W.D. Fard: Unveiling the Identity of the Founder of the Nation of Islam*. Cambridge: Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2019.

Advance Journal of Current Research

Adv. J. C. Research

Vol. 11; Issue 5;

May-2026

ISSN: 2323 -1744

Impact Factor: 8.30

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/ajcr/index>

Norrell, Robert J. *Up from History: The Life of Booker T. Washington*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2009.

Ross, Marlon B. *Manning the Race: Reforming Black Men in the Jim Crow Era*. New York: New York University Press, 2004.

Samuels, Wilfred, and Gregory S. McCue. *The Critical Response to Malcolm X*. Westport, CT: Greenwood Press, 1996.

Savage, Barbara Dianne. *Your Spirits Walk Beside Us: The Politics of Black Religion*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2008.

Van Deburg, William L. *New Day in Babylon: The Black Power Movement and American Culture, 1965-1975*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1993.